

USING SONGS AND MUSIC TO TEACH LISTENING**Jizzakh branch of National University of Uzbekistan****named after Mirzo Ulug`bek****The Faculty of Psychology, the department of Foreign languages****Philology and foreign languages****Scientific advisor: Teshaboyeva Nafisa Zubaydulla qizi****nafisateshaboyeva@gmail.com****Student of group 101-23: Xoldorova Rayxona Erkin qizi**

Annotation: The article aims to show the benefits and strategies of using songs and music to teach English to learners and improve their listening abilities. Incorporating songs and music creates an enjoyable and captivating learning environment that motivates learners to actively engage in listening activities. Through exposure to authentic language in songs, learners develop listening comprehension skills, expand vocabulary, and refine pronunciation. Additionally, songs provide opportunities for the development of effective listening strategies and foster cultural awareness. By harnessing the power of songs and music, educators can create a dynamic and effective language learning experience for learners, ultimately enhancing their listening skills in an engaging and enjoyable manner.

Key words: authentic materials, non-authentic materials, song, music, communicative competence, vocabulary expansion, cultural awareness.

You know that listening is one of the main skills in learning foreign language, especially, learning with songs and music. Listening is the ability to hear attentively and to understand what others are saying. When we define listening it is necessary to consider listening components such as: understanding of the accent; the way words are pronounced; grammar rules; and learning vocabulary which helps to understand the whole meaning of what the transmitter is saying in context.

Effective listening depends entirely on the relationship between these components. A disconnection amongst these factors would make listening less effective. If one listens to a certain message, he/she must combine such factors in context to react more accurately to what he/she is listening to. Harmer (2001) states that “What a good listener is able to do is to process what he hears on the basis of the context it occurs in.”

Students need to be taught strategies in discriminating different accents and the importance of idioms and jargon including speech rhythms which will enable them to listen to the various styles of spoken English in conversation with a native speaker, listening to songs or watching films. Harmer (1998) explains: One of the main reasons for getting students to listen to spoken English is to let them hear different varieties and accents — rather than just the voice of their teacher with its own idiosyncrasies. In today’s world, they need to be exposed not only to one variety of English.

The way words are pronounced also has implications on language comprehension because the listener should be able to differentiate the sounds he/she hears. This ability is necessary given that there are words that have similar pronunciation. As students listen to words they create mental pictures. If they cannot correctly discriminate sounds of the words they hear, their mental images will be incorrect and they will formulate either a confused or wrong meaning of the message.

Some people confused the meaning between hearing and listening. According to Stephen, Lucas (1998) listening does not mean we do not hear, and they come to explain the process of hearing to be a physiological one arguing that: “It involves the vibration of sound wave on our eardrums and the firing of electrochemical impulses from the inner ear to the central auditory system of the brain, but listening involves paying close attention to, and making sense of, what we hear.”

Activities to Accompany a Song:

According to Valdés Marín (2005) an activity is a type of educational organizational procedure to stimulate learning based on an actual or potential

involvement of mental functioning, directed to develop abilities to a certain level with a medium level of student's independence. It is a type of procedure that involved more than one action by the student or students who develop it.

The following activities are closed to the listening stages: You can split your listening activities into the following three categories: gist, scan and detailed tasks. These create stepping stones for the students towards gaining a thorough understanding of the lyrics.

Most of the activities require a minimal response, like writing one word or circling true or false, meaning that students are focused on listening and not on writing out an answer.

Gist: Also known as a skim task, the idea of a gist activity is for students to get the song's overall meaning. This task often takes the form of a question. Here are some gist activities:

Sum Up: Give students no information about the song, simply play it and ask them to sum up the main idea in one sentence.

Ask a Question: Tell students what the song is about before playing it, and pose a question for them to think about while listening, such as "Is the man happy with his life?" or "What is for sale in the window?"

Multiple Choice Questions: Ask a question with a multiple choice answer, like "Whose birthday is it? a) Mark b) Laura c) Ramon." When they hear the answer, students can write their choice down, or throw a ball into a corresponding bucket.

Scan: The purpose of a scan activity is for students to find out specific pieces of information about the song. Here are three scan activities:

Questions: Give students a worksheet with five specific questions to answer as they listen. For example, "What color is the boy's scarf?" or "What is the name of the road they walk down?"

Complete the Sentences: On the board, write the first half of three sentences from the song. When students hear each sentence, they must choose from options to complete the second half of the sentence.

Fill in the Blanks: Provide students with a gap-fill worksheet to complete as they listen. If necessary, provide a word bank at the top of the page.

Detailed Comprehension: These tasks check whether students have gained a more in-depth understanding of what the song is about.

Correct the Sentences: Provide students with a set of statements, all of which are slightly incorrect. As they listen to the song, students must fix the statements to make them correct.

True or False: Give out a set of true or false statements about the song, making sure that the true ones are not exactly the same as the lyrics. For example, if the song says “The boy was delighted with his rocking horse,” you could write the statement, “The boy was happy with his toy.” This is where the comprehension comes in, as students cannot simply listen to buzz words, but must understand the meaning of the lyrics. As students listen they must choose if the statements are true or not.

Matching: Students can complete a matching task as they listen to the song, like matching pictures of people with the opinions they expressed.

Conclusion: There are other difficulties placed on the teacher. To maintain variety in the classroom, the teacher needs a good repertoire of songs. Although learners feel happy listening and singing the same song several occasions, the interest in same song can be lost if this one is used too many times. To sum up, I can say that using songs and music in teaching listening is very useful and can cause not to be bored while learning for learners.

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